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Perception and Satisfaction of Library Services: A Comparative Study of Medical College Libraries in Peshawar, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Medical Colleges play a vital role in the production of medical facilities for the enhancement of quality health services. There are Seventeen (17) medical colleges working in the public and private sector of the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The purpose of this study is to measure the effectiveness of medical college libraries and user's perception and satisfaction regarding the utilization of resources and services by users of Khyber Medical College and Kabir Medical College libraries. Data was collected through a questionnaire using five Likert scales to judge the level of perception and satisfaction of library users. Analysis has been carried out and found that the Khyber Medical College has the highest resources, a well-equipped and automated library with the latest facilities. Most of the library users of Khyber Medical College library perception is that "the library is an important part of the institution" However, most of the library users of Khyber Medical College and Kabir Medical College libraries suggested some improvement in parking, expansion in timing, increase in facilities, services and staff.

INTRODUCTION

Medical libraries are considered special libraries, as their mission and vision are for specific groups of people and subjects. They are also called special libraries because of the specific resources they hold like health information resources. Mabawonku (1998) explains health information as those materials, facts, or news communicated to people, which help maintain mental, and physical health. It should therefore be able to filter information from the available maze of information, package them for effective use, and as such become for the users, a source of rapid access for the retrieval and transfer of information and a focal center that emphasizes the importance of information and knowledge towards the resolution of human health needs (Anyauku, 2008). To assess, in general, is to determine the importance, size, or value to evaluate. Library staff assesses operations by collecting, interpreting, and using data to make decisions and to improve customer service. They study internal processes, levels and quality of service, and library impact on institutional goals.

Palmour (1980) noted that continuous assessment of library services helps library administrators check how well the library fits into the organization it is serving, how it serves the current users, and whether there are new audiences to recruit and introduce to what the library has to offer, above all it helps the possibility of determining whether and where there is room for improved or additional programs and services in the future. In the medical libraries, assessment is taking place at all levels in the medical librarianship, (Holtz, 1993) stated that administrators are concerned with issues such as demonstrating the effective use of scarce resources to meet user needs and meet institutional expectations. De Genaro (1984) predicted that there is a need to evaluate medical libraries because, in no distant time, the excellence and usefulness of a library will be measured not only by the state and quality of its collections but also by the range of services that its staff can deliver to users by conventional and electronic means from a growing variety of services. Users will no longer ask what a library has, but what services it can provide.

It is the government's responsibility to take accountability, collect all the resources, and spend on education through proper and useful yet stable and feasible education about all spheres of life health awareness with the latest technology equipment and modern trends information of all fields and disciplines. For a stable awareness requirement, certain institutional libraries are necessary to provide resources and services for their capacity

building regarding their required fields. Such institutional libraries are playing a vital role as a backbone for the development of the nation. For this purpose, multiple institutes have been established all over the country. Some of them are working under the federal government and some are practicing under the leadership of provincial govt. Apart from that some other non-government organizations are working through public and private partnerships.

All institutes are working for the betterment of the country. Libraries play a leading and centered role in providing resources and services to the institutions. All three types of libraries are working all around the world in Pakistan Public, Special, and Academic libraries.

Medical Colleges play a vital role in the production of medical facilities for the enhancement of quality health services. There are Seventeen (17) medical colleges working in the public and private sectors in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Two libraries have been selected to know the users' perception and satisfaction with the utilization of resources, services, facilities, and modern trends of Medical College libraries, especially Khyber Medical College and Kabir Medical College library.

Research Questions

1. What is the users' perception regarding library use?
2. Are the users satisfied with the services offered by the library?
3. Are the users satisfied with the library staff's behavior?
4. Are users satisfied with the facilities available in their respective libraries?
5. What are improved resources and services according to the present needs of the Institute?

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the last few years, the role of libraries has been changed, Hanif, S., Shah, Rehman and Hassan (2024) specifically in medical libraries are taking lead in academic for medical students and professional development for faculty members. For the improvement of library services, it is very essential to give due attention to the perception of library users.

Hussain and Kumar (2013) stated that “medical libraries are indispensable for supporting the academic journey of students and faculty, clinical practice, and continuous professional education” at the same time if libraries are fail to fulfill the users need it will also lead the negative perception which as a result will reduce the frequency of library use.

Adekunmisi (2013) and Ojedokun et al. (2015) explored the perception of library users on their personal experiences and they mentioned that “Medical students expect access to current medical journals, textbooks, and digital databases, which are pivotal for their academic and clinical needs”. Malik and Mahmood (2016) found that “user satisfaction correlates positively with access to a diverse range of medical literature”. Ismail et al. (2019) assert that “well-designed library spaces that facilitate study and collaboration enhance user experiences”. Literature has explored that library hours are another key factor influencing user perception. Ali and Shah (2018) explained: “Medical students often require access to library resources outside of traditional hours, particularly during examination periods”. Harinarayana and Raju (2010) “Students often gauge their satisfaction based on their interactions with library staff”. Adeyemi et al. (2014) recorded that libraries that robust digital services and friendly access to electronic resources are

receiving positive feedback from users.

Khan et al. (2020) surveyed Khyber Medical College and identified that the majority of students consider the library as an essential institution, they further stated that the availability of medical journals, a parking facility, and automated services are required for the library users. In the same way (Hussain & Rehman, 2019) explored the perception of Kabir Medical College and mentioned that users are less satisfied with fewer digital resources and they are also not satisfied with the professionalism of the staff. Abbas and Nazir (2021), also shared a comparison of public and private sector medical college libraries. "private institutions generally reported higher satisfaction levels due to better resources and personalized services compared to their counterparts in public libraries" Mathews, (1981) mentioned in his book "graduate students use the library in essentially the same way, while use by undergraduates is different". Gabriella, (1999) mentioned that popular services "such as circulation, interlibrary loan, document copy preparation, and local reading are well-known" (Robbins & Kathryn, 2001) investigated the reference services quality in the libraries of health sciences.

Sturgis, Paul mentioned in an article in 2003 "Technology libraries can archive considerable resources of detailed information about their users" Southborough University, 2000-2002, investigated the issues about privacy in digital library environment. Findings suggested that "users had low levels of anxiety about privacy when using libraries, but this was because they expected that libraries would not pass on personal data to other bodies"

Zhai, and Xiaojuan discussed the underlying internal problems existing in libraries that affect user satisfaction. (Cook & Thompson, 2000) explained that "there is increasing pressure on libraries to demonstrate the provision of quality services. "The ISO standard is customer and process-oriented and it includes criteria for identifying customer requirements and measuring customer satisfaction with the organization's performances" (ISO/FDIS, 1997; International Standards Organization, 1998). Misbah (2012) researched on libraries and stated that "no progress can be made in any field, especially in Science and technology without special libraries holding the latest material/research". So the previous work on medical libraries clearly indicated the user perception and satisfaction is highly imported for the betterment of medical libraries.

METHODOLOGY

Two special libraries of Public and Private organizations were selected for comparison of the resources, and services. The perception of the users of the Medical College libraries was also evaluated through an approved questionnaire. Five-point Likert Scale (1-Strongly Agree, 2- Agree, 3-Nutral 4-Disagree, 5-Strongly Disagree) was used. Another Likert scale (1-Twice a day, 2-Weekly, 3-Monthly, 4- Yearly, 5-Never) was also used. Institutional information was obtained from the administration of the concerned department of the concerned Institutions. The remaining data was obtained from the official websites of the concerned departments using the Internet Explorer browser using Google Search. Boolean operators (and, or, not) were also the part of methodology Techniques during searching the data. Information regarding literature review and general information was obtained through Google Scholar, Yahoo, Library Information Science and Technology Abstract, and Higher Education Commission (HEC) Digital Library.

RESPONDED PROFILES

The respondents' profiles focused on gender, age, job title, professional qualification, number of years worked, and experience in the library environment.

TABLE 1: GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS (N=77)

"Gender"		<i>frequency</i>	Percentage
1.	Male	69	69
2.	Female	31	31

Results from table 1 on gender show that out of the 100 respondents who responded to the questionnaire 69(69%) were male and 31 (31%) were female.

TABLE 2: TYPE OF UNIVERSITY/INSTITUTE (N=77)

"Type of University/Institute"		<i>frequency</i>	Percentage
1.	Public Sector	46	46
2.	Private Sector	54	54

Results from table 2 on gender show that out of the 100 respondents who responded to the questionnaire 46 (46%) for Public Sector while 54(54%) were Private sector.

TABLE 3: KHYBER MEDICAL COLLEGE =1

"Perception library use"	<i>about</i>	Strongly Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Neutral <i>f (%)</i>	Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	Strongly Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	M	SD
1. Libraries enhance my quality of life		41(41)	41(41)	6(6)	6(6)	6(6)	20	17.14
2. The staff members at the Library are helpful and professional		18(18)	47(47)	0(0)	29(29)	6(6)	20	16.79
3. Library has the materials that I need		18(18)	24(24)	6(6)	41(41)	12(12)	16.2	13.33
4. Library opens in convenient hours		35(35)	41(41)	6(6)	18(18)	0(0)	20	15.91
5. I am satisfied with the services provided by the Library		24(24)	41(41)	6(6)	29(29)	0(0)	20	15.05
6. library's building space is adequate for my needs		41(41)	35(35)	6(6)	18(18)	0(0)	20	15.91
7. Library is impotent to me		76(76)	24(24)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	20	15.91

Kabir Medical Kabir
college =2

<i>“Perception library use”</i>	<i>about</i>	Strongly Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Neutral <i>f (%)</i>	Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	Strongly Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	M	SD
1. Libraries enhance my quality of life		33(33)	53(53)	0(0)	7(7)	7(7)	20	19.98
2. The staff members at the Library are helpful and professional		20(20)	33(33)	0(0)	33(33)	13(13)	19.8	12.54
3. Library has the materials that I need		20(20)	27(27)	0(0)	53(53)	0(0)	20	19.69
4. Library opens in convenient hours		33(33)	40(40)	0(0)	27(27)	0(0)	20	16.84
5. I am satisfied with the services provided by the Library		20(20)	40(40)	0(0)	13(13)	0(0)	14.6	14.85
6. library’s building space is adequate for my needs		60(60)	27(27)	0(0)	27 (27)	0(0)	22.8	22.18
7. Library is impotent to me		93(93)	7(7)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	20	36.60

Both colleges highly value their libraries and recognize their importance in enhancing the quality of life. Khyber Medical College demonstrated better satisfaction with staff professionalism, while Kabir Medical College excelled in terms of the adequacy of building space. Kabir Medical College users seem to be slightly more satisfied overall, particularly with the adequacy of library space and the importance of the library. However, dissatisfaction with staff professionalism was notably higher at Kabir Medical College compared to Khyber Medical College.

TABLE 4: KHYBER MEDICAL COLLEGE =1

<i>“Library Use by Different Ways”</i>	Strongly Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Neutral <i>f (%)</i>	Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	Strongly Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	M	SD
1. Visited the Library in person to use materials or services	35(35)	40(40)	6(6)	6(6)	12(12)	19.8	14.70
2. Used a personal computer from your	6(6)	24(24)	64(64)	0 (0)	6(6)	20	23.43

home, or office to access the library materials or services								
3. Contacted the library by phone to use its services	6(6)	12(12)	82(82)	0(0)	0(0)		20	31.32
4. Purchased a book from either a physical or online bookstore	18(18)	6(6)	0(0)	41(41)	35(35)		20	23.43
<i>Kabir Medical College =2</i>								
“Library Use By Different Ways”	Strongly Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Neutral <i>f (%)</i>	Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	Strongly Disagree <i>f (%)</i>		M	SD
1. Visited the Library in person to use materials or services	40(40)	33(33)	7(7)	7(7)	13(13)		20	13.83
2. Used a personal computer from your home, or office to access the library materials or services	6(6)	20(20)	67(67)	0(0)	7(7)		20	24.39
3. Contacted the library by phone to use its services	13(13)	13(13)	73(73)	0(0)	0(0)		19.8	27.23
4. Purchased a book from either a physical or online bookstore	7(7)	0(0)	60(60)	0(0)	33(33)		20	23.40

A significant portion of respondents from both KMCs visit the library in person (Khyber: 75%, Kabir: 73%), though Kabir Medical College shows slightly higher agreement on this. The majority of respondents from both KMCs prefer accessing library materials via personal computers from home or office, with 64% from Khyber Medical College and 67% from Kabir Medical College remaining neutral on this. Kabir Medical College shows a slightly higher disagreement regarding remote access. Most respondents from both colleges (82% at Khyber and 73% at Kabir) show neutrality or lack of engagement with contacting the library by phone, highlighting the potential underutilization of this service. Khyber Medical College respondents demonstrate a mixed stance, with 41% disagreeing and 35% strongly disagreeing with purchasing books from bookstores, whereas 60% of Kabir Medical College respondents were neutral.

TABLE 5: ASPECTS OF THE LIBRARY THAT MAY INFLUENCE YOUR USE
Khyber Medical College =1

“Aspects of the library”	Strongly	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly	M	SD
	Agree <i>f</i> (%)	<i>f</i> (%)	<i>f</i> (%)	<i>f</i> (%)	Disagree <i>f</i> (%)		
1. I Would use my library more if the staff were more knowledgeable	35(35)	35(35)	6(6)	18(18)	6(6)	20	13.0
2. I Would use my library more if the staff were more available to help me	12(12)	41(41)	6(6)	0(0)	6(6)	13	14.5
3. Would use my library more if the library had more of the CDs and DVDs that I want	28(28)	18(18)	18(18)	24(24)	12(12)	20	5.51
4. I would use my library more if the library had more computer stations	41(41)	18(18)	18(18)	24(24)	0(0)	20.2	13.15
5. Would use my library more if the library building was more inviting/ pleasant	41(41)	12(12)	12(12)	29(29)	6(6)	20	13.01

Kabir Medical College =2

“Aspects of the library”	Strongly	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly	M	SD
	Agree <i>f</i> (%)	<i>f</i> (%)	<i>f</i> (%)	<i>f</i> (%)	Disagree <i>f</i> (%)		
1. I Would use my library more if the staff were more knowledgeable	40(40)	27(27)	0(0)	27(27)	6(6)	20	14.79
2. I Would use my library more if the staff were more available to help me	13(13)	47(47)	0(0)	20(20)	13(13)	18.6	15.60
3. Would use my library more if the library had more of the CDs and DVDs that I want	33(33)	13(13)	13(13)	20(20)	13(13)	18.4	7.79
4. I would use my library more if the library	53(53)	13(13)	14(14)	13(13)	7(7)	20	16.69

had more computer stations							
5. Would use my library more if the library building was more inviting/ pleasant	80(80)	20(20)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	20	30.98

This comparative summary analyzes responses regarding key aspects of the library at Khyber Medical College (KMC) and Kabir Medical College (KMC). Respondents were asked to rate their agreement on whether improvements in specific areas of the library would lead to increased usage. While both institutions share similar concerns and areas for improvement, Kabir Medical College shows a more unanimous demand for changes, particularly in creating a more pleasant library environment. Khyber Medical College also highlights a need for improved staff support and resources but with more varied opinions across different areas.

TABLE 6: PERSONAL USE OF THE FOLLOWING LIBRARY SERVICES
Khyber Medical College =1

“Personally used library services”	Yes f (%)	No f (%)	M	SD
1. Located materials I used for my enjoyment	65(65)	35(35)	50	15
2. Located materials that were used for business	18(18)	82(82)	50	32
3. Located materials I used to conduct a job search	18(18)	82(82)	80	32
4. Used a personal computer in the library to access the internet	41(41)	59(59)	50	9
5. Contacted a Librarian to help me answer a question	24(24)	76(76)	80	26
6. Attended an organization or community meeting at the library	47(47)	53(53)	50	3
7. Attended a library program or event for adults	18(18)	82(82)	50	32

Kabir Med. Col=2

“Personally used library services”	Yes f (%)	No f (%)	M	SD
1. Located materials I used for my personal enjoyment	60(60)	40(40)	50	10
2. Located materials that were used for business	20(20)	80(80)	50	30
3. Located materials I used to conduct a job search	27(27)	73(73)	50	23
4. Used a personal computer in the library to access the internet	73(73)	27(27)	50	23
5. Contacted a Librarian to help me	20(20)	80(80)	50	30

answer a question				
6. Attended an organization or community meeting at the library	40(40)	60(60)	50	10
7. Attended a library program or event for adults	20(20)	80(80)	50	30

Both K.M.C (65%) and Kabir Medical College (60%) have relatively high usage of the library for personal enjoyment. A lower percentage of respondents from both colleges use the library to locate business-related materials (KMC: 18%, Kabir: 20%). More respondents from Kabir Medical College (27%) reported using the library for job searches compared to Khyber Medical College (18%). Kabir Medical College (73%) shows a much higher usage of personal computers for internet access compared to Khyber Medical College (41%).

Both institutions show low participation in adult programs (KMC: 18%, Kabir: 20%).

TABLE 7: OPINION ABOUT FUNDING

Khyber Medical College=1

<i>“Opinion about funding”</i>	Yes <i>f (%)</i>	No <i>f (%)</i>	M	SD
1. Improved parking	65(65)	35(35)	50	15
2. Expanded hours	71(71)	29(29)	50	21
3. Enlarged/remodeled facilities	65(65)	35(35)	50	15
4. Increased services and staff	59(59)	41(41)	50	9

Kabir Medical College=2

<i>“Opinion about funding”</i>	Yes <i>f (%)</i>	No <i>f (%)</i>	M	SD
1. Improved parking	73(73)	27(27)	50	23
2. Expanded hours	80(80)	20(20)	50	30
3. Enlarged/remodeled facilities	73(73)	27(27)	50	23
4. Increased services and staff	80(80)	20(20)	50	30

Both medical colleges express strong support for increased funding across all areas, with Kabir Medical College showing a higher overall demand, particularly in the areas of expanded hours and staff/services improvement.

TABLE 8: LIBRARY IS AN IMPORTANT PART OF MY INSTITUTION

Khyber Medical College =1

<i>“Library is an important part”</i>	Strongly Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Neutral <i>f (%)</i>	Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	Strongly Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	M	SD
1. The Library is an important part of my Institution	80(80)	10(10)	5(5)	2(2)	3(3)	20	30.13

Kabir Medical College =2

<i>“Library is an important part”</i>	Strongly Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Agree <i>f (%)</i>	Neutral <i>f (%)</i>	Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	Strongly Disagree <i>f (%)</i>	M	SD

1. The Library is an important part of my Institution	76(76)	8(8)	8(8)	4(4)	2(2)	19.6	28.29
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The perception of the library as an integral part of the institution is highly positive in both medical colleges, with minor differences in levels of agreement. Both colleges can confidently build upon this strong support for the library's role in the institution.

CONCLUSION

Comparative analysis has been carried out and it was found that the two libraries are well established. Khyber Medical College library has the highest human, financial, and material resources, well-equipped infrastructure of Information technology with its latest facilities of air conditioner, generator back up, Mosque and toilet. Well trained staff of the library is also available to facilitate the users.

Kabir Medical College (KMC) Library is placed at second number within the resources, services, equipment, and modern trends of technology. It has a large number of magazines and journals. It has sufficient resources for abstracts, indexes, research papers, and reports on different subjects.

Most of the library users of twin Medical College libraries perceive that the library is an important part of their institutions. It has increased our quality of life. The library has material that we require for the enhancement of health education for the delivery of the best health services to Pakistani society. They also explained that they have used library material for educational, business, personal, and enjoyment purposes.

However, most of the library users of Khyber Medical College and Kabir Medical College library have suggested some improvements in parking, expansion in time, and increase in facilities, services, and staff. A proper annual budget for the smooth running of the library is a must for the library. The purchase of library software is very necessary for the automation of the library material. Recruitment of library professional and semi-professional staff is a need of the time.

There should be an increase in general textbooks. The library is the best place to study because its staff can monitor all matters, especially silence. This basic rule must be addressed immediately and people who availed of library services should be cautioned of penalties if silence is broken.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study of user perceptions and satisfaction with medical college libraries, particularly in Khyber Medical College (KMC) and Kabir Medical College (KBMC), several key recommendations can be made to improve the quality of library services, resources, and facilities.

- Quick access to online medical databases, e-books, e-journals, and other digital resources must be provided to the medical libraries. Moreover, the latest digital content is important for the staff and students.
- Library collections should be updated regularly to meet users' academic and research needs.
- Easy access must be provided to specialized databases like PubMed, Up-to-date, and other peer-reviewed journals, which are essential for medical education and research.
- More and better study spaces must be provided to accommodate more users,

especially during exam periods. Dedicated quiet zones should also be expanded for focused study.

- Latest and more computers with access to medical software and databases should be a top priority. Moreover, strong and reliable Wi-Fi access throughout the library must be ensured.
- The library's automated system should be expanded to borrowing books and other services to reduce the time wait.
- Library services should be provided to the medical library for longer hours. Especially for the exam preparations. Expanding weekend hours, especially for students with clinical responsibilities during weekdays, would accommodate more users.
- Additional staff especially during busy times to provide personalized assistance with research will fulfill faculty and student's needs.
- Qualified staff also needs professional development training sessions. This will allow them to offer expert guidance to users seeking academic support.
- Library services must be users centered for this purpose regular surveys must be conducted.
- A dedicated help desk service should be provided where users can get real-time support with research queries, database navigation, or technical issues.
- Promotion and marketing of library services should also be increased.
- Regular orientation programs for new students and faculty must be conducted to introduce the library's resources and services. These sessions should include guidance on how to access digital resources, use databases, and search for materials effectively.
- Online and social media presences should also be enhanced. These platforms can be used to announce new acquisitions, promote workshops, and highlight special events or services.
- Special and specialized Workshops and Training should be conducted for users.
- Offer regular workshops on how to conduct medical research, access specialized databases, and use reference management tools like EndNote or Mendeley.
- regular training on proper citation techniques, plagiarism avoidance, and ethical use of information to support academic integrity must be done.

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